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Emotional Intelligence As Correlates Of Teachers Work Attitude In Khana Local Government Area Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated emotional intelligence as correlates of teachers work attitude in public secondary schools in Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State. A sample of 400 teachers was drawn using simple random sampling and proportionate sampling techniques. Three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Two instruments were used for the study; Emotional intelligence scale and the Teachers Works Attitude Scale (TWAS). Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Statistics and Multiple Regression Statistics. Result of the study showed that there was a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude. It also indicated that gender did not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude, while age significantly moderated the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of teachers in khana Local Government. Based on the findings, recommendations were made, that employers of labour should include emotional intelligence measures in their recruitment process and also in-serve training on emotional intelligence should be subsequently organized by school authorities.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, work attitude, Teachers

INTRODUCTION

It is an indisputable fact that the teachers are an important figure and authority at all levels of educational systems. This is because apart from his inestimable primary role in curriculum implementation, his opinions about his jobs as well as the behaviour towards the student both in the classroom and outside the classroom are all issues of great concerns.

The feelings that a teacher has about his job as well as his behaviour patterns displayed in doing his job determine how dedicated, committed and effective he will be in doing his job. This behaviour pattern or attitude of the teacher exert immense influence on students learning as well as on their overall academic achievement orientation.

Emotional intelligence is an ability to recognize one's own feeling and those of others for motivating self as well as one's relationship with others. Emotional intelligence was defined by **Mayer and Salovey** (2004) as one's own ability to understand and regulate one's own emotional response as well as adopt and respond to others. Emotional intelligence is concerned with understanding oneself and others, relating to people adapting to and coping with immediate surroundings and to be more successful in dealing with environmental demands. **George** (2002) observed that an emotionally intelligent person has the ability to understand the emotions of others and manage their moods in the social settings. He added that teachers

who have low emotional intelligence for effective achievement in the teaching and learning process. Emotional intelligence as defined by **Goleman** (2006) is the ability to identify, understand, use and manage ones and emotional state effectively.

This involves an intellectual process that leads to the use of emotional feelings to motivate, plan and achieve. Therefore, emotional intelligence can be basically be described as an interconnection between feelings and things. **Goleman** (1995), argued that intelligence quotient (IQ) was not the only critical factors that determines individuals' success instead, he believed that people emotional intelligence played a large, role on success in life and on the job. "Without emotional intelligence, a person can have the best training, an analytical minds and endless supply of ideas but will not make a great leader" (**Goleman, 2001**). It is assumed that employees with high emotional intelligence are likely to exhibit the right attitude towards their jobs, therefore, teachers with high emotional intelligence are likely to have a positive attitude towards their job.

Attitude determines what each individual will see, hear, think and do. Furthermore, attitude means the individual's prevailing tendency to respond favorably or unfavorably to an object (person or group of people, institutions or events (Morris & Maisto, 2005).

Attitude can be either positive or negative. According to Kreither & Kinicki (2007), there are three components of attitude: Affective, cognitive and behavioral. The affective component is a feeling or an emotion one has about an object. or a situation, the cognitive component is the belief or ideas one has about an object or situation, whereas, the behavioral component of attitude reflects how one intends to act or behave towards someone or something. In most cases, the three components appear concomitantly to shape teacher's classroom posture, through direct and indirect interaction between society, school and teachers (Leite, 1994).

Attitude towards work means perceptions that affect how employees perform in their positions. Brophy & Good (1997) proposed that teachers' attitude and expectations impact upon their students' educational outcome. A positive attitude is key to maintaining a positive classroom environment. "A teacher's positive attitude does cause a chain reaction of positive thoughts, events and outcome" (Harts, 2008). According to Jones (2002), "the number one reason for the passion that teachers shared was their ability to make positive differences in the lives of young people". In addition, most of the professionals who taught felt that their ability to contribute to society while helping others, made teaching a rewarding profession. Studies have revealed that emotional intelligence has a positive relationship with work attitude. In a study carried out by Barranta (2011) to investigate emotional intelligence and personality traits of Filipino seafarers and their attitude towards work environment, the result indicates high positive relationship between emotional intelligence and attitude towards work environment.

Meisler (2010) conducted a study to examine the effects of emotional intelligence on aspects of organizational politics employee's work attitudes, formal and informal behaviour, feeling of justice, burnout and the likes. The result revealed that emotional intelligence empowers positive attitudes and weakens negative attitudes. Salami, (2007), concluded in his study that emotional intelligence and self-efficacy had significant relationship with work attitude among teachers. Also, a study by Carmeli (2003) indicated that emotional intelligence augments positive work attitude. Rohana, Jusoff & Abdul (2009) examined the relationship between emotional intelligence of university staff to work attitude. There was no significant difference in scores of male and female. The con-elation between emotional intelligence and work attitude was higher for males, compared to females but both had the same probability value of .000 which shows a significant relationship between the variables. The result also revealed that age is not correlated to emotional intelligence and work attitude.

Statement of the problem

Emotional intelligence is a very important quality that every teacher is supposed to possess. In our public secondary schools today, some teachers exhibit poor attitude towards their job. This poor attitude over the years have been attributed to different factors such as poor salary structure, lack of motivation, poor administrative leadership, lack of recognition by general society, and so on. This has led to low productivity higher absenteeism, increased work errors, inability to cover scheme of work, not attending

to lesson periods promptly hostility towards students, colleagues and even parents and guardians. When this happens students and the school authorities suffer unpleasant outcomes as much work is left undone. Many teachers feel that they can only be satisfied with their jobs when their basic and social needs are satisfied. They attribute positive work attitude to fat salaries, promotion and so on, thereby neglecting the usefulness of some psychological factors. Though all teachers work under similar conditions, some still exhibit positive attitude and remain committed to their job while others are not. Based on this, it is likely that apart from salary and other conditions of service, there may be other personal aspects of the teacher's life (like emotional intelligence) that may date to his attitude towards work. Few studies had given attention to the contribution of psychological factors (such as emotional intelligence) to work attitude of secondary school teachers in Rivers State, therefore, the researcher intends to fill that gap. It is for this reason that there is need to carry out a research to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and work "attitude among secondary school teachers in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on this background, the following research questions were answered to obtain the result Of the study;

1. What is the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers?
2. Does gender moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers?
3. Does age moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude?

The following null hypotheses, tested at 0.05 level of significance, were formulated to guide this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers.
2. Gender does not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers.
3. Age does not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers.

METHOD

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the 821 teachers in public secondary schools in Khana Local Government Area. A sample of 400 public secondary school teachers drawn using simple random sampling technique and proportionate sampling method was used for the study. Two instruments were used for the study namely; the emotional intelligence scale (EIS) developed by Schutte, Malouff, Hall, Haggerty, Cooper, Golden & Dornheim (1998) and the teacher work attitude scale (TWAS) developed by the researcher. The emotional intelligence scale contained 33 items while the work attitude scale contained 10 items. Items on the two instruments were presented as statements to which respondents were required to indicate their levels of agreement or disagreement on a 4 point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). In order to ensure face and content validity, the two instruments were given to the researcher's supervisor and two other experts in the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling. These experts determined whether the items contained in the instruments were adequate enough for the study. Also, they ensured the items measures what it purports to measure. Language difficulty level was also ensured so as to make sure that it is neither too high nor low for the population being studied. The reliability of the two instruments were determined through the test-retest method and the following stability coefficients were obtained for the various instruments: Emotional dligence-0.86 and Work attitude-0.81. The coefficients so obtained were high enough to guarantee the use of the instruments as reliable for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and multiple regression statistics were used for data analysis.

RESULTS

Results of the study are presented in tables as shown below

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between emotional intelligence and work attitude

(r ²) Variables	N	Mean	Std. D	r	r	Squared	Sig.
Work attitude	33.28	3.70	400	.930			
Emotional Intelligence	111.008	11.48			.86	.004	

Table 1 showed a correlation coefficient (r-value) of .930 which indicated a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude, which was found to be statistically significant at a sig-value of .004 and 0.05 alpha level, therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the variables was rejected.

Table 2: Regression analysis showing the moderating impact of gender on the relationship between Emotional intelligence and work attitude

a. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.167	.028	.023	3.65254

b. Anova

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	151.810	2	75.905	5.690	0.58
Residual	5296.387	397	13.341		
Total	5448.197	399			

c. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		Beta			
(Constant)	31.775	1.811		17.544			.000
Emo intel	-.003	.018	-.008	-.142	.002		
Emo intel x Gender	.010	.003	.170	3.048	.087		

Table 2(a) showed a multiple regression (R) of .167 and a regression squared (R²) of .028. This showed that gender accounted for 2.8% of the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude. Table 2(b) showed no significant moderating impact of gender on the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude as $F(2, 397) = 5.690$ at 0.58 significant level and 0.05 alpha level. Table 2(c) showed the Beta values of each variable on the relationship. Emotional intelligence had a beta value of -.008 at a significant level of .002 while the interaction effect (emotional intelligence x gender) had a beta value of .170 at a significant level of .087 and 0.05 alpha level. This however showed that gender did not significantly moderate the relationship between the variables, since $p > 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis which stated that gender does not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude as accepted.

Table 3: Regression analysis showing the moderating impact of age on the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude.

a. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.199	.040	.035	3.63016

b. Anova

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	216.501	2	108.251	8.214	.000
Residual	5231.696	397	13.178		
Total	5448.197	399			

c. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		Beta			
(Constant)	32.047	1.801	17.790	.000			
Emo intel	-.005	.017	-.016	-.292	.045		
Emo intel x Age	.008	.002	.206	3.783	.000		

Table 3(a) Showed a multiple regression (R) of .199 and a regression squared (R²) of .040. This showed that age accounted for 4% of the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude. Table 3(b) showed a significant moderating impact of age on the relationship between emotional intelligence and work. attitude as $F(2, 397) 8.214$ at .000 significant level and 0.05 alpha level. Table 3(c) showed the Beta values of each variable on the relationship Emotional intelligence had a beta value of -.016 at a significant level of .045 while the interaction effect (emotional intelligence x age) had a beta value of .206 at a significant level of .000 and 0.05 alpha level. This however showed that age significantly moderated the relationship between the variable, since $p < 0.05$ Hence the null hypothesis

which stated that age does not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work was rejected.

Summary of findings

- The relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude was Positive and statistically significant.
- Gender did not significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude.
- Age significantly moderated the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude.

DISCUSSION

The results of data analyzed indicated that emotional intelligence had a Positive relationship with work attitude and the relationship was found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of probability. This result is in agreement with those of Barranta (2011), Meisler (2010), Salami (2007) and Carmeli (2003) who also found out that emotional intelligence is Positively related to work attitude. However, no study with Contrary findings was found. The result also indicated that there is no significant moderating impact of gender on the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of secondary school teachers at 0.05 level of probability. Furthermore, the result indicated that there is a significant moderating impact of age on the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude of Secondary school teachers at 0.05 level of probability. This finding is similar to those of Rohana et al (2009) and Seyed et al (2012), who also found that age does significantly moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study have indicated that emotional intelligence plays a significant role in teachers work attitude. Therefore, the issue of being emotionally intelligence should be addressed in order to produce better quality teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- Employers of labour should include emotional intelligence measures in their recruitment process so as to ascertain the applicant's level of possession of the competency.
- In-service training should be subsequently organized by the school authorities in order to continuously improve the level of teachers' emotional intelligence.
- Emotional intelligence should be emphasized by the school administrators for both male and female, young and old teachers, that is, no group should be left out in the training. The teachers' level of emotional intelligence has to be given boost at all times.
- Seminars and workshops should be organized by the school authorities, inviting professional resource persons like Guidance Counsellors and Educational Psychologists.
This will go a long way in improving not only the teachers' attitude, but also that of the students.

Suggestion for further studies

This study covered only public secondary school teachers in Obio-Akpor local government area of Rivers state. Therefore, it is suggested that further studies could be carried Out on the role of emotional intelligence on work attitude of university lecturers. Also other variables such as years of experience, marital status and educational qualification could be used to find out whether they moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitude.

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